

Technostress Among DepEd Teachers and Their Teaching Performance: Basis for Intervention Design

Judith C. Mustaham

Teacher III Baliwasan Senior High School -Stand Alone Department of Education, Division of Zamboanga City

INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 pandemic has caused a high level of technostress in teachers. When implementing blended learning using digital technology, teachers frequently suffer a condition known as technostress throughout the process of integrating new technologies. According to recent studies, educators have experienced stress as a result of needing to change to offer online courses (Etxebarria et al., 2021, 1). The present study investigates the level of technostress among elementary, secondary and senior high school teachers of the Department of Education during the COVID-19 pandemic and their teaching performance. The findings of the study will be utilized by the researcher to craft an intervention design to address the technostress experienced by the teachers.

Admittedly, learners may profit from the use of digital technologies in blended learning. But they could also put less tech-savvy teachers under more pressure and create technological stress for them (Jena 2015,1; Hatlevik 2018,1). Indeed, Technostress is a contemporary adaption illness that affects workers and is brought on by an incapacity to manage the new computer technology in a healthy way (Merced & Franco 2015,1). In their study, it revealed that there were low levels from overload, invasion, complexity, insecurity and uncertainty.

Similarly, in the study of Lee (2018,1) on technostress in the Philippines, the results showed that participants had a somewhat greater level of teacher efficacy and a moderate degree of technostress and stress management.

DepEd Memorandum 004 s. 2022 on the implementation of the Results-based Performance Management System (RPMS)- Philippine Professorial standards for teachers for school year 2021-2022, specifies the objectives that are observable and non-observable in the classroom during the classroom observation of teacher performance. The vast majority of teacher performance evaluations are conducted by the school principal using the Classroom Observation Tool (COT) Rating Sheet and Inter-observer Agreement Form. Aside from the school principal, the assistant principal and department heads who are master teachers can do the classroom observation.

Therefore, evaluating teachers' performance is essential to determining their ability; this is not a simple process that can be accomplished by looking only at students' academic success. The evaluation procedure itself will increase the efficacy and practice of teachers, which will benefit the teacher workforce (Robinson 2022,1).

Longman (2013,1) revealed that instructors' levels of technological stress were low. Additionally, it was noted that teachers who were very adept at integrating technology into their lessons experienced low levels of technostress, but those who spent an excessive amount of time figuring out and organizing the use of technology in the classroom were said to have high levels of technostress. The performance of the teachers is also impacted by this. The results of these assessments should ideally be utilized to inform teachers' professional growth and provide them feedback. Thus, it is decided that teacher performance evaluations are required.

The Department of Education (DepEd), specifically the Baliwasan Senior High School Stand-Alone in Zamboanga City Division, implemented blended learning during the pandemic period. Majority of the teachers chose online and offline resources, though blended learning utilized radio or television aside from using modules. Per observation of the researcher, teachers were facing technostress in meeting their online classes; they had a lot of difficulties in coping with the demands of online learning. Most of them who handled online classes during the pandemic period experienced technostress.

The study aimed to assess the level of technostress in terms of tecno-overload, techno-invasion, techno-complexity and techno- uncertainty and their relationship to the performance of senior high school teachers. It has policy implication by addressing workload issues and by providing support for teachers to manage digital tasks effectively. This could involve

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implementing policies to limit after-hours communication, streamlining administrative tasks through technology, and providing tools to automate repetitive tasks.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Technostress of teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic. Technostress is defined as "an adaptation problem experienced by an individual who finds it difficult to adjust to new technology." The word "technostress" is defined as the use of terms like "technophobia" and "computer anxiety" (Laspinas 2015,1).

According to Longman (2013,1), instructors who received technology instruction had lower levels of technostress, and that teachers who used unreliable technology had greater levels of technostress.

Similarly, according to Tarafdar et al. (2011, 1), gender significantly impacted technostress. Teachers' overall levels of technostress were gender-neutral, with medium levels of technostress experienced by both male and female educators.

Also, Longman (2013,1) examined the levels of techno-stress among teachers with less than ten and more than ten years of experience, finding no discernible relationship between the two. Tarafdar et al. (2011,1) asserted that while employees with greater experience had lower levels of technostress because they were more adept at managing stress, younger users were more accustomed to technology in information-related occupations. According to this viewpoint, teaching experience and technological proficiency counterbalance each other in terms of technostress.

Furthermore, it has been discovered that technostress has a negative effect on performance (Tarafdar et al., 2014,1). In a study that was similar, Coklar et al. (2016,1) reported that teachers' overall levels of technostress were medium level. Regarding sub-scales, teachers reported medium levels of learning-teaching process oriented, technical issue oriented, and social oriented technostress, as well as low levels of profession oriented and personal oriented stresses. Teachers' overall technostress levels varied according to the average Internet use time variable but did not differ based on gender or length of service.

Techno-overload of teachers in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. Techno-overload takes place when the use of information system makes professionals work faster (Tarafdar et.al., 2007,1).

Similar to this, technology overload comprises three components: interruption overload, information overload, and system feature overload. It is defined as "device proliferation and/or information overload that causes cognitive and physical burdens on human beings due to the use of multiple gadgets with multiple functions to accomplish multiple tasks in everyday activities" (Karr-Wisniewski and Lu 2010,1).

When it comes to communication technology, interruption overload refers to the extent to which users experience an excessive amount of disruption from spontaneous interactions or the cessation of work due to interactions that they did not initiate (Yin et al., 2018).

Ragu-Nathan et al. (2008,1) highlighted the potential risk of techno overload, which refers to the increased and intensive workload brought on by technology use. Known as a techno-stressor, techno-overload is linked to stressful circumstances that force people to work longer and faster than usual. However, one factor that contributes to technological stress and has a good correlation with teachers' job performance is techno-overload (Li and Wang, 2021).

According to Curbano's (2019,1) study, when it came to respondents' assessments of technostress, techno-overload received the highest rating, meaning that users were overloaded with work and knowledge as a result of the advancements in technology employed in the workplace. This suggests that people expected to be more productive and efficient in a technologically advanced workplace, which would reduce the amount of manual labor.

Techno-invasion of teachers in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. Techno-invasion refers to circumstances in which teachers' personal lives are intruded upon by work-related ICT as a result of ICT forcing them to be reachable at all times and continuously linked (Li & Wang 2021,1).

Techno-invasion is characterized by continuous connectedness across time and space, ensuring that workers are always available to accept requests for employment (Gaudio et al., 2017).

According to Wu et al.'s study (2020,1), techno-invasion is a strong predictor of job anxiety, while employee computer self-efficacy and perceived organizational support can both greatly reduce this relationship. More significantly, we discover that when employees feel low levels of perceived organizational support, computer self-efficacy has a stronger moderating influence.

Techno-invasion is on the rise, according to Diller et al. (2016,1).

both favorable and unfavorable reactions to stress. Research indicates that the function of individual resources as mediators in the stressor-response link is significant. Surprisingly, the six resources that were studied had different effects on stress reactions.

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For people who could not manage their time and online activities in a disciplined manner, techno-invasion can lead to technostress (Habaradas 2015,1).

Techno-complexity of teachers in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. Techno-complexity refers to circumstances in which the intricacy of ICT makes teaching more challenging and necessitates that teachers continuously pick up and relearn skills to deal with problems related to rapidly evolving or complex technology. (Wang and Li, 2021).

Information system techno-complexity is related to the need for professionals to invest time and energy in learning and comprehending new applications; increased vendor pressure to use the newest hardware, software, and applications; and increasingly complex technical capabilities and terminology related to information systems. As a result, users may feel overwhelmed and find it difficult to comprehend the diversity of apps, features, and language (Tarafdar et al., 2007).

Studies that have already been conducted on teachers' attitudes toward technology refer to this as their perceptions of the tools' perceived utility and simplicity of use. Users will be more appreciative of technology if they find it easy to use.

Techno-complexity and techno-insecurity significantly impacted instructors' work performance negatively when it came to the impact of technostress on their work (Li and Wang 2021,1).

The degree of technological complexity can be measured by comparing the relative importance of the good and negative outcomes, which vary throughout the three types of technology use cases: using a computer and internet, a laptop, and a mobile device. Students are most likely to experience negative effects while using a mobile device with internet access, according to a frequency study of the positive, negative, and net implications of utilizing technology in the classroom (Gorra et al., 2016).

Techno-insecurity of teachers in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. The results of the study of Califfs (2020,1), revealed that burnout is noticeably increased by technological complexity, insecurity, invasion and overload.

Similar to this, Alam's (2015,1) study examined three technostress factors: techno-complexity, techno-uncertainty, and techno-overload. It discovered that these factors had a stronger negative correlation with employee productivity when the employee was more equity-sensitive and role-overloaded.

Teacher performance evaluation.

The technique to evaluating teaching performance from the standpoint of professional development, taking into account that this role is essential to enhancing meaningful and long-lasting learning (De Almeida 2017,1).

For the sake of the efficacy of their profession, teachers must put in long hours of supervision, evaluation, lesson planning, and testing preparation both within the classroom and at home, according to Torreon and Trabajo (2019,1). Due to this circumstance, there is a higher level of stress, which can negatively impact their work and lead to occupational stress.

A teacher's physical, mental, and emotional health may suffer as a result of excessive stress, which may also have an impact on the teacher-student relationship, teacher performance, and/or student performance. This is according to Mingoa (2017,1).

According to Betonio (2015, 1), instructors frequently experience stress or burnout, which has a negative impact on their ability to teach. In general, stress is the unfavorable response that each individual has when faced with a high level of pressure and other demands on their ability to adjust.

Public elementary and secondary schools often conduct teacher performance reviews. A teacher's effectiveness and success in the classroom are factors in their evaluation. Review and rating of teachers' work is done formally in schools through evaluation. In a similar study, Catolos & Catolos (2017,1) discovered that the majority of respondents had teaching performance that is extremely satisfactory.

Research Questions

This study determined the level of technostress among DepEd teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic in three chosen DepEd schools and their teaching performance in S.Y. 2021-2022.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of technostress among DepEd teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic in terms of:
 - 1.1 techno-overload
 - 1.2 techno-invasion
 - 1.3 techno-complexity and
 - 1.4 techno-insecurity?
2. What is the level of teaching performance of DepEd teachers?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of technostress among DepEd during the COVID-19 pandemic when data are grouped according to their profile?

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4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of technostress among DepEd teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic and their teaching performance?
5. What intervention program can be crafted on the basis of the findings?

Research Participants

This study involved teachers from Baliwasan Central School (School A), Baliwasan Senior High School Stand-Alone (School B) and Zamboanga National High School-West (School C) of Baliwasan District, Zamboanga City Division, Zamboanga City, during the 2nd semester of school year 2021 – 2022. A total of 208 teachers were involved in this study. Majority of the respondents are females; they are between 21 years and above in the teaching service and they are from School C. Slovin's formula, using simple random sampling was utilized in this study.

METHODOLOGY

This study is a descriptive-quantitative type of research employing survey methods and document. The design was used to determine the relationship between technostress and the performance of teachers in school year 2021-2022. It is quantitative research as it deals with quantitative data and analyzed using statistical tools (Creswell cited in Hector 2008,1).

The study utilized an adapted survey-questionnaire from *Springer Nature Singapore Pte Ltd. 2017 T*. However, the researcher removed some statements and added new statements to fit into the context of the study. The Interview Guide consists of 2 questions in relation to how the senior high school teachers cope with technostress during the COVID-19 pandemic. The research instrument was validated by a panel of experts who were preferably doctorate degree holders. The survey -questionnaire was subjected to Cronbach Alpha reliability test. The following statistical tools were utilized in the study: Frequency and Percentage, Mean, ANOVA, T-Test and Pearson-r

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Level of Technostress among Senior High School Teachers during the COVID-19 Pandemic in terms of Techno-Overload

A. Techno-Overload	Mean	Description
1. I use technology to do more works than I can handle.	4.07	High level
2. I use technology despite tight schedules.	4.10	High level
3. I change my habits to adapt new technologies.	4.09	High level
4. I have a higher workload because of technology.	3.68	High level
5. I feel fatigued due to overwork using my laptop day and night.	3.88	High level
Overall Mean	3.96	High level

Legend: 4.21 -5.00 = Very high level 3.41 – 4.20 = High level 2.61 – 3.40 = Moderately high, 1.81 – 2.60 = low level, 1.00 – 1.80 = very low level

As shown in table 1, an overall weighted mean of 3.96 is generated by the teacher-respondents which indicates that the level of technostress among DepEd teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic in terms of techno-overload is high. The results support the study of Curbano (2019,1), which shows that respondents' assessments of technostress and techno-overload were greatest, indicating that users faced work and information overload as a result of workplace technology advancements.

Table 2: Level of Technostress among Senior High School Teachers during the COVID-19 Pandemic in terms of Techno-Invasion

B. Techno- Invasion	Mean	Description
1. I have to be available due to this technology.	4.30	Very high level
2. I have to give my time to keep current on new technologies.	4.02	High level
3. I feel my personal life is being invaded by this technology.	3.63	High level
4. I have a lot of academic concerns due to this technology.	3.74	High level
5. I need to embrace new technologies to cope with the demands of time.	4.19	High level
Overall Mean	3.99	High level

Legend: 4.21 -5.00 = Very high level, 3.41 – 4.20 = High level 2.61 – 3.40 = Moderately high, 1.81 – 2.60 = low level, 1.00 – 1.80 = very low level

As shown in table 2, an overall weighted mean of 3.99 is generated by the teacher-respondents which indicates that the level of technostress among DepEd teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic in terms of techno-invasion is high.

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The results corroborate the claims made by Li & Wang (2021), who claimed that techno-invasion refers to circumstances in which teachers' personal lives are intruded upon by work-related ICT since it forces them to be reachable at all times and linked continually.

Table 3. Level of Technostress among Senior High School Teachers during the COVID-19 Pandemic in terms of Techno-Complexity

C. Techno- Complexity	Mean	Description
1. I know how to manipulate technology.	3.93	High level
2. I need to use new technology.	4.37	Very high level
3. I have to upgrade my technology skills.	4.20	Very high level
4. I need to spend more time to use technology.	4.21	Very high level
5. I have to understand the complex of new technology.	4.03	High level
Overall mean	4.15	High level

Legend: 4.21 -5.00 = Very high level, 3.41 – 4.20 = High level 2.61 – 3.40 = Moderately high, 1.81 – 2.60 = low level, 1.00 – 1.80 = very low level

As shown in table 3, an overall weighted mean of 4.15 is generated by the teacher-respondents which indicates that the level of technostress among DepEd teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic in terms of techno-complexity is high level. Techno-complexity refers to circumstances in which the intricacy of ICT makes teaching more challenging and necessitates that teachers continuously pick up and relearn skills to deal with problems related to rapidly evolving or complex technology. (Wang and Li, 2021).

Table 4. Level of Technostress among Senior High School Teachers during the COVID-19 Pandemic in terms of Techno-Insecurity

D. Techno- Insecurity	Mean	Description
1. I feel threatened to my job security due to new technologies.	3.43	High level
2. I have to update my technology skills to avoid being left behind.	3.66	High level
3. I am threatened by co-teachers with newer technology skills.	3.41	High level
4. I need to acquire additional knowledge in technology to boost my confidence.	3.80	High level
5. I feel there is a need for training in technology for fear of criticism.	3.67	High level
Overall Mean	3.59	High level

Legend: 4.21 -5.00 = Very high level, 3.41 – 4.20 = High level 2.61 – 3.40 = Moderately high, 1.81 – 2.60 = low level, 1.00 – 1.80 = very low level

As shown in table 4, an overall weighted mean of 3.59 is generated by the teacher-respondents which indicates that the level of technostress among DepEd teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic in terms of techno-insecurity is high level. The findings corroborate those of Califf (2020, 1), whose research demonstrates that burnout is greatly increased by technological overload, invasion, and insecurity.

Table 5. Level of Teaching Performance of DepEd Teachers

Level of Teaching Performance	Rating	Interpretation
	4.299	Very Satisfactory

Legend: 4.5-5 - Outstanding, 3.5-4.49 - Very Satisfactory, 2.5-3.49- Satisfactory, 1.5-2.49 - Unsatisfactory and Below 1.5 - Poor

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Table 5 shows that the level of teaching performance of DepEd teachers is very satisfactory as reflected in the overall mean of 4.299. Regarding the impact of technological stress on educators' job performance, Li & Wang (2021) found that technological complexity and instability significantly harmed their performance.

Table 6. Significant difference in the level of technostress among DepEd teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic when data are grouped according to their sex

Level of Technostress	Sex	Mean	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Techno-Overload	Male	4.1098	.165	.685	Not significant
	Female	3.8428			
Techno-Invasion	Male	4.0295	.698	.404	Not significant
	Female	3.9034			
Techno-Complexity	Male	4.5410	13.738	.000	Significant
	Female	3.9921			
Techno-Insecurity	Male	3.5779	.531	.467	Not significant
	Female	3.6042			

Significant level at $\alpha = 0.05$

Table 6 shows the result of the Independent Sample t-test on the significant difference in the level of technostress among teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic when data are grouped according to their sex. It is revealed in the table that the Techno-Overload has the t-value = .165 with p – value = .685, Techno-Invasion has the t-value = .698 with p – value = .404 and Techno-Insecurity has the t-value = .531 with p – value = .467. Since all the p-values > 0.05, the significant difference did not exist, hence the hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in the level of technostress among DepEd teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic when data are grouped according to their sex is accepted. This implies that regardless of their gender, they experienced technostress in terms of techno-Overload, techno-Invasion, and techno-Insecurity during the COVID-19 pandemic.

However, Techno-Complexity, with the t-value = 13.738 with p – value = .000 which is less than the alpha value of 0.05 indicates that the significant difference exists. Hence, the hypothesis in which there is no significant difference in the level of technostress among senior high school teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic when data are grouped according to their sex is rejected. This means that the DepEd male teachers have high level of techno complexity. They can perform better than females in terms of manipulating the technology.

The finding supports He and Freeman (2010,1) whose finding in their study revealed that females feel less confident with computers because they have learned less and practiced less and feel more anxious about using computers when compared with male counterparts.

Table 7. Significant difference in the level of technostress among DepEd teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic when data are grouped according to their length of service

Level of Technostress	Length of Service	Mean	F-value	p-value	Interpretation
Techno-Overload	1-5 years	4.0794	3.651	.007	Significant
	6-10 years	4.0446			
	11-15 years	4.0022			
	16-20 years	3.6667			
	21 years and above	3.7433			
Techno-Invasion	1-5 years	4.2222	2.018	.003	Significant
	6-10 years	3.9622			
	11-15 years	4.0000			
	16-20 years	3.5778			
	21 years and above	3.7343			
Techno-Complexity	1-5 years	4.2571	1.336	.258	Not Significant
	6-10 years	4.3514			
	11-15 years	4.2000			
	16-20 years	4.1889			

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	21 years and above	3.9172			
Techno-Insecurity	1-5 years	3.6444	.873	.481	Not Significant
	6-10 years	3.5676			
	11-15 years	3.3826			
	16-20 years	3.3889			
	21 years and above	3.6795			

Significant level at $\alpha = 0.05$

Table 7 shows the result of One-Way ANOVA on the significant difference in the level of technostress among DepEd teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic when data are grouped according to their length of service. It is evident in the table that Techno-Overload has F-value = 3.651 with .007 and Techno-Invasion has F-value = 2.018 with p-value = .003, which the p-values are less than the significant level of alpha of 0.05 indicates that the significant difference exists. Hence, the hypothesis which states that "there is no significant difference in the level of technostress among DepEd teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic when data are grouped according to their length of service" is rejected. This means that teachers who have been in the service for 1 to 5 years experienced Techno-Overload and Techno-Invasion. Johnson et al. (2016,1) assert that one of the main factors influencing schooling nowadays is technology. It is expected of schools to employ technology to improve student learning.

Table 8. Significant difference in the level of technostress among DepEd teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic when data are grouped according to their School

Level of Technostress	School	Mean	F-value	p-value	Interpretation
Techno-Overload	School A	3.8878	7.701	.001	Significant
	School B	4.3030			
	School C	3.8380			
Techno-Invasion	School A	3.8865	6.135	.003	Significant
	School B	4.5576			
	School C	3.8043			
Techno-Complexity	School A	4.4568	6.312	.002	Significant
	School B	4.5621			
	School C	3.9725			
Techno-Insecurity	School A	3.3667	2.419	.022	Significant
	School B	3.8061			
	School C	3.5975			

Significant level at $\alpha = 0.05$

Table 8 shows the result of One-Way ANOVA on the significant difference in the level of technostress among DepEd teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic when data are grouped according to their school. It is evident in the table that Techno-Overload has F-value = 7.701 with .001, Techno-Invasion has F-value = 6.135 with p-value = .003, **Techno-Complexity** has F-value = 6.312 with p-value = .002 and **Techno-Insecurity** has F-value = 2.419 with p-value = .022 which all the p-values are less than the significant level of alpha of 0.05 indicates that the significant difference exists. Hence, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in the level of technostress among DepEd teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic when data are grouped according to their school" is rejected. This means that School B teachers experienced Techno-Overload, Techno-Invasion, Techno-complexity and Techno-Insecurity most. The finding holds true to the study of Jomud et al., (2021,1) that teachers have high level of workload and burnout. Indeed, teaching profession has high demands of stress.

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Table 9. Significant relationship between the level of technostress among DepEd teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic and their teaching performance

Variables		r- value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Level of technostress	Teacher's teaching performance	0.201	.004	Reject Ho	Significant

*Significant level at $\alpha = 0.05$

Table 9 shows the result of Pearson-r on the significant relationship between the level of technostress among DepEd teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic. It is shown in the table that the level of technostress and teachers' teaching performance with r- value = 0.201 with p-value of .004 which indicates that the significant relationship exists. Hence, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant relationship between the level of technostress among DepEd teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic and their teaching performance" is rejected. The study's conclusion contrasts with that of Hero (2019, 1), whose research showed that the use of technology in the classroom significantly improved social studies instructors' ability to teach. Additionally, professional practice and productivity were the key indicators of technological integration.

Intervention Program

The intervention program designed in accordance with this question is seminar-Workshop on Technostress Management for DepEd Teachers. This is a one-day activity to help the teachers in decreasing their level of technostress. The Objectives are the following: gain insights on the nature and danger of technostress towards health; apply the coping mechanisms on how to fight technostress; do the Yoga meditation; and conduct team building activities.

Implications

This finding implies that teachers experience techno-overload nowadays, since teachers meet their classes using online platforms in the absence of face-to-face meetings with the learners. Teachers do not have a choice but to utilize technology since DepEd adapts blended learning and the use of technology is deemed necessary for the delivery of instruction. They feel invaded in their personal lives due to the demands of technology. They spend much time keeping current on new technologies in order to comply their academic concerns. Teachers need to cope with the complexity of technology as this is very useful in the present educational system. They need to upgrade their skills in ICT for them to be more efficient and effective teachers. The techno-insecurity cannot be denied among teachers who still lack the skills in the manipulation of technology. They feel the need to enhance their skills in technology through training so that they will not be left behind. Teachers did their performance very well despite the challenges brought about by technostress in this pandemic period. This implies that teachers who are still new in the teaching service are still struggling in embracing the educational system such as the use of e-class record, online platforms, and integration of ICT in class as one of the mandated teacher's competencies. Analysis suggested that DepEd teachers who were employed for less than 5 years are not yet adjusted to the system. They rely on technology to do more work. Despite the heavy works in school, they manage to adopt the new technologies. They consider higher workload because of technology. Teachers in this school are experiencing technostress most because it is a large school which comprises of 3500 students and yet there are only 67 teachers, hence, teachers are overloaded with teaching loads and workloads. The level of technostress among senior high school teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic has low positive correlation with their teaching performance. Furthermore, the level of technostress among senior high school teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic along the above-mentioned dimensions can be good predicting variables to explain their teaching performance. The data imply that, when all the variables of the level of technostress among DepEd teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic were taken altogether, the relationship did manifest on the teaching performance. Although DepEd teachers encountered techno stress, they still have very satisfactory performance.

CONCLUSION

The level of technostress among DepEd Teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic in terms of techno-complexity, techno-invasion, techno-overload and techno-insecurity was high. The level of teaching performance of DepEd teachers was very satisfactory. There was no significant difference in the level of technostress in terms of Techno-Overload, Techno-Invasion, and Techno-Insecurity among DepEd teachers when data were grouped by sex. However, in terms of Techno-Complexity, there was a significant difference. There was no significant difference in the level of technostress in terms of techno-complexity and techno-insecurity among DepEd teachers when data were grouped by length of service. However, a significant difference existed in techno-overload and techno-invasion. There was a significant difference in the level of technostress in terms of techno-overload,

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techno-invasion, techno-complexity and techno-insecurity among DepEd teachers when data were grouped by school. There was a significant relationship between the level of technostress among DepEd teachers and their teaching performance. A Seminar-Workshop on Techno-stress Management for DepEd Teachers may be implemented as intervention program.

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following are hereby recommended: 1.) The Schools Division Superintendent may support the intervention program to be implemented by the schools through his approval and recommendation. In addition, he may add teachers to schools that lack teaching force so that teachers will not be overloaded with teaching loads. 2.) The Division Research Council may support the intervention program through endorsement to all districts. 3.) The Public Schools District Supervisors and Education Program Supervisors may disseminate the information to all school heads regarding the implementation of the intervention program and do the monitoring to ensure its success. 4.) The Policymakers may support teachers in preventing too much technostress. This support may be particularly useful during challenging times, such as during the pandemic where blended learning has been implemented and utilization of ICT has dominated the teachers' job. 5.) The School Heads may support the intervention program by requiring all teachers to participate and cooperate in the implementation of the intervention program. In addition, they may also reduce the teaching loads of teachers who are carrying overloads so that they will not experience high level of technostress. 6.) The DepEd Teachers may support the intervention program through active participation as this will also benefit them in relation to their wellness and health. They may consider yoga meditation and other strategies recommended for them to reduce high level of technostress. 7.) The students need to cooperate with their teachers, considering the bulk of work that teachers do in this pandemic period.

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